

Impact of Blood Hemorheological Properties on Nephropathy in Patients with Multiple Myeloma

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Background. Renal impairment is one of the most common and clinically significant complications of multiple myeloma (MM), occurring in approximately 50% of patients at disease onset. About 20% of patients develop renal failure, and 10% require renal replacement therapy. Furthermore, renal dysfunction may arise during treatment, particularly in patients with relapsed or refractory MM.

Objective. To evaluate the impact of blood hemorheological properties on the development of nephropathy in patients with multiple myeloma living in Uzbekistan.

Methods. A comprehensive clinical and laboratory assessment was conducted in 124 patients diagnosed with multiple myeloma. Blood plasma viscosity, serum creatinine, glomerular filtration rate (GFR), β_2 -microglobulin levels, paraprotein concentration, and signs of renal involvement, including proteinuria and nephrotic syndrome, were analyzed. Correlations between hemorheological parameters and indicators of renal dysfunction were assessed. A risk stratification scale for nephropathy development was developed based on clinical and laboratory variables.

Results. Elevated plasma viscosity (>4.5 mPa·s) was detected in 68 of 124 patients (54.8%) and was significantly associated with increased serum creatinine levels (>120 μ mol/L) and reduced GFR (<60 mL/min). The prevalence of nephropathy was significantly higher among patients with hyperviscosity than among those with normal viscosity parameters (47.1% vs. 18.6%, $p<0.05$). Patients with severe paraproteinemia (IgG >35 g/L) demonstrated plasma viscosity values of 6.2–6.8 mPa·s, accompanied by proteinuria and nephrotic syndrome. In the high-risk group (≥ 9 points), nephropathy developed after a mean period of 14.2 ± 3.1 months following diagnosis, compared with 34.7 ± 5.6 months in the low-risk group. A positive correlation was identified between β_2 -microglobulin levels and blood viscosity ($r_s=+0.43$; $p<0.01$). Elevated β_2 -microglobulin levels were associated with a significantly increased risk of hyperviscosity (RR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.22–2.59; $p=0.006$). Based on these findings, a risk assessment model incorporating serum creatinine, GFR, β_2 -microglobulin, proteinuria, and hypercalcemia was developed, allowing stratification into low- (0–4 points), intermediate- (5–8 points), and high-risk (≥ 9 points) categories.

Conclusion. Blood hyperviscosity is significantly associated with the development and progression of nephropathy in patients with multiple myeloma. Incorporation of plasma viscosity measurements into nephropathy prediction models improves sensitivity from 72% to 84% and enables earlier identification of patients who may benefit from interventions aimed at reducing hyperviscosity, including plasmapheresis, hydration, and control of paraproteinemia. Early implementation of these measures may contribute to preservation of renal function and reduction of disability.